

Deliverable D1.4

Data Management Plan

Project Title	A real-time mobile multimodal positron emission tomography and multiphoton endoscopic technology for REalistic in-field quantitative IMAGING of CROPS
Project Acronym	RE-IMAGINE-CROPS
Project Number	101187260
Project Start Date	1-May-2025
Project Duration	36 months

WP N° and Title	WP1: Coordination and Outreach
WP Leaders	Rafael Diaz (EURO-BIOIMAGING)
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	EURO-BIOIMAGING (EURO-BIOIMAGING)
Dissemination Level	PU – Public
Contractual Delivery Date	31-10-2025 (M6)
Actual Delivery Date	31-10-2025 (M6)
Authors	Rafael Diaz, Nicola D'Ascenzo
Contributors	
Reviewers	Katja Bühler

Change Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
v1	28.10.2025	Rafael Diaz, Nicola D'Ascenzo	Initial draft

Acronyms and Abbreviations

DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DMP	Data Management Plan
DX.X	Deliverable
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IT	Information Technology
ME	Multiphoton Endoscopy
nrrd	Nearly-Raw Raster Data
OVGU	Otto-von-Guericke-University Magdeburg
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
v	Version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Introduction	4
2. Description of work	4
2.1. Data Summary	4
2.2. Open Science and FAIR Data	5
2.2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	5
2.2.2. Making data accessible	5
2.2.3. Making data interoperable	6
2.2.4. Increase data re-use	6
2.3. Other research outputs	6
2.4. Data security and sustainability	6
2.5. Ethics	7
2.6. Other issues	7
3. Conclusion	7

Executive Summary

This report presents the overall structure and key elements of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project. It outlines the nature of the data to be generated during the project, as well as the procedures for its collection, processing, and management. The report details how the consortium will ensure compliance with the FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) throughout the project's lifecycle. Finally, it describes the planned mechanisms for data sharing beyond public project outputs, and the strategies for maintaining and preserving the data after the project's completion.

1. Introduction

The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project is part of the European Innovation Council (EIC) through the Pathfinder Open Call and is led by the project coordinator, Euro-BioImaging. The consortium is a partnership of 8 beneficiaries, with representation of Austria, Italy, Finland, France, and the Netherlands. The project started on 1 May 2025 and will continue until April 2028.

RE-IMAGINE-CROPS seeks to transform agricultural practices through innovation in Digital Precision Agronomy. The primary objective of the project is to develop the first mobile imaging technology for in-field measurement of biophysical processes in crops, thereby enabling more effective crop management practices.

The development of the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS prototype will require the collection, processing, analysis, use, storage, and dissemination of agricultural data. To ensure responsible and efficient data handling, a Data Management Plan (DMP) is essential.

The DMP outlines the procedures the project team will follow for acquiring, storing, and sharing data throughout the project's duration. It serves as a comprehensive guide for all data-related activities, ensuring compliance with best practices, ethical standards, and Horizon Europe requirements for data management. The DMP will be updated throughout the project if needed, and a final version will be shared at the end of the project as a deliverable (D1.9, month 36).

2. Description of work

2.1. Data Summary

The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project is centred on the development and application of a multimodal imaging platform that integrates Positron Emission Tomography (PET) and Multiphoton Endoscopy (ME) to study plant systems at complementary spatial scales. PET imaging enables functional, whole-plant insights at organ level, while ME provides high-resolution structural and cellular-level data in the order of micrometres. Both imaging modalities acquire data from adjacent regions of the same specimen, making spatial and contextual alignment between modalities critical for meaningful interpretation and analysis.

To facilitate this integration, the project will implement a data registration strategy based on artificial intelligence. Specifically, unsupervised learning techniques will be employed to align the PET and ME images by matching local structural descriptors extracted from both modalities. This approach removes the need for manually annotated correspondence data and enables flexible, scalable training across diverse datasets.

2.2. Open Science and FAIR Data

The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project will be implemented in accordance with the principles of transparency, openness, and active engagement of all relevant stakeholders throughout the development and prototyping of the imaging technology.

All software developed and data generated within RE-IMAGINE-CROPS will be made available through recognised open science platforms, such as GitHub. This includes all software tools, workflows, terminologies, ontologies, and underlying algorithms, which will be released under Open Access for research and educational purposes.

2.2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In RE-IMAGINE-CROPS, all datasets will be assigned a persistent identifier to guarantee traceability and long-term accessibility. Since this is the first time such imaging data is being generated, the design will maximise discoverability and allow users to apply it across a wide range of contexts. Each plant image will be accompanied by agronomic observations, a still image, and relevant experimental documentation. A dedicated database compiling this information will be delivered as a project output, and will be available as a Nature dataset.

2.2.2. Making data accessible

Initially, all data will be stored in the IEEE dataport (<https://ieee-dataport.org>). However, as previously mentioned and to ensure wider use and impact, the imaging data, namely dynamic PET data co-registered with ME data, will be deposited in a suitable database. Code will be deposited in a shared repository such as GitHub and made publicly available under an open source license after securing related IP either through patent applications or the publication of the scientific methods and results at scientific conferences or in appropriate journals.

2.2.3. Making data interoperable

The data obtained in this project will be stored in non-proprietary formats widely used by the scientific community. In particular,

- PET imaging data will be stored in DICOM format.
- ME data, the annotations and co-registered PET and ME data will be stored in .nrrd format.

2.2.4. Increase data re-use

In line with the project's commitment to open science and dissemination of results, all datasets generated, along with their corresponding metadata, will be made publicly available and reusable by third parties at the end of the project. All necessary information for data validation, e.g., code and other software, will be managed and shared during the project through private code repositories. After its public release, code and directly usable versions of the software, with tutorials and examples, will be published on open-source platforms such as GitHub. Additionally, all data will be licensed under Open Data Commons.

Data quality during acquisition of information and processing will follow all standard procedures relating to the corresponding imaging techniques and agronomy procedures. This implies that the quality standards and associated descriptions shared above will be adjusted as necessary throughout the project.

2.3. Other research outputs

The digital plant PET system developed during the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project will be available at BF Educational (BFEDU) and at the Otto-von-Guericke-University Magdeburg (OVGU); the software developed will be accessible.

2.4. Data security and sustainability

The partner institution BFEDU has a data preservation team composed of 3 IT experts responsible for data management. All project data and software will be for at least 15 years in the BFEDU in-house data management system.

2.5. Ethics

No major ethical discussions are applicable.

2.6. Other issues

We do not foresee any other potential issues.

3. Conclusion

This report outlines the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project. It establishes the standards and procedures governing the acquisition, handling, analysis, and sharing of all data generated during the project. The plan will be regularly reviewed and updated to reflect the project's progress and any emerging requirements.

European
Innovation
Council

**Funded by
the European Union**

The RE-IMAGINE-CROPS project has received funding from the EIC Pathfinder Open program under grant agreement ID 101187260. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.